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Young Submarine Lava Flow Identified at 6 km Depth on the Mid Cayman Rise

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A fresh, very lightly sedimented lava flow with fresh, unaltered glassy rinds was discovered on the northern portion of the Mid-Cayman Rise (MCR) during the Deep Submergence Vehicle (DSV) ALVIN Science Verification Expedition (SVE) in Aug 2022, making it currently Earth's deepest known lava flow visited in situ by human observers. The MCR is an ultraslow spreading ridge in the Caribbean Sea thought to represent a series of extensional oceanic core complexes (Hayman et al, 2011). The young eruption deposit is formed entirely of pillow lava of a variety of morphologies (elongate, bulbous, bread-crust textured, flattened pillows) as a function primarily of emplacement slope (steeper to less steep, respectively). Many of the pillows are highly ornamented with glassy extrusions (e.g., pillow buds and toes). Alvin Dive 5097 traversed 1 km of sea bed astride a ridge, staying entirely within the young lava flow terrain. The lava samples collected are mostly very sparsely olivine phyric (1-3 mm crystals) and to first order, devoid of vesicles, except in the cores of pillow ornaments, as is common at other sites. However some of the lava samples, especially those collected from drained pillow rims, exhibit variable-sized and shaped ovate voids commonly thought to form from external water-magma interaction when found at shallower depth. The lavas differ substantially in age, morphology and petrology from a plagioclase ultraphyric collapsed lobate lava sample found nearby on a different dive, 1 km shallower, at the Beebe hydrothermal field. The implication of these characteristics will be discussed in light of the great eruption depth and spreading systematics.

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